

INSIGHTS FROM ECONOMICS INTO COPYRIGHT AND COMPETITION LAW

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This essay was written for those attending the CREATE Spring School in April, 2024 on Platforming Creativity. The programme mostly had a focus on IP and competition law relating to platforms. My Keynote talk, based on this essay, was intended to show how economics approaches these topics.

Introduction

Every academic discipline has its rules and conventions on the scope and analysis of its content and how to incorporate changes over time - its methodology. Economics has a very broad scope within which there are many specialist branches: IP and competition mostly use industrial economics, which is part of microeconomics.

I believe that one of the difficulties of doing inter-disciplinary work is that we do not easily comprehend the underlying methodologies of different academic disciplines. This essay is an attempt to explain how economics is applied to digitisation, copyright and regulation in the creative industries.

Economic methodology

Economics has been applied systematically to copyright for well over 50 years. The concepts and theories of economics have been applied to analyse the role of copyright in the economic organisation of industries in which copyright operates and to evaluate it as a policy measure. My interest in copyright is its claim to enable creators and performers to earn income from their work.

It is a fundamental part of the economist's methodology that propositions have to be testable. Does copyright in fact enable authors and other creators to earn money from their work? If so, that justifies it as a policy tool. How much do they earn? As we now know, the top few do very well from copyright earnings while the vast majority do not earn enough to survive in their chosen

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occupation. So, there are two issues: copyright does what it is intended to do but not sufficiently well to financially support all who are eligible.

The crucial distinction in economics between positive and normative economics, ie between efficiency and equity, is relevant here. The difference hangs on whether a value judgement has to be made. Efficiency propositions can be tested, equity ones cannot. So does copyright enable authors to earn from their work? the answer is 'yes'. Is that income fair or equitable? That requires a value judgement so we cannot say. What economics can do, though, is to research royalty earnings and look at their distribution, then compare them to average earnings in the economy. That has switched a normative question into a positive one. (At this point, I'd like to note that legal statements about copyright consistently confuse the two, frequently referring to equity without defining it, while in practice essentially leaving it to the market to decide what is equitable).

Is copyright an economic incentive?

Economics is basically about incentives: what motivates people to produce and consume goods and services. In a market economy, incentives are mostly monetary – prices and other payments. Royalties from copyright are the reward for the effort and inspiration on the part of authors and performers for their work. They are intended as an incentive to authors to produce works of art, literature, music etc. (Landes 2020). But is copyright an *ex ante* incentive or an *ex post* reward? Not knowing in advance how great the reward might be introduces risk into the decision.

It is widely known that royalty earnings are very unevenly distributed, with 'superstars' dominating what have come to be called 'winner takes all' markets. Most professional creators and performers know that success is far from certain, either in terms of work or income. To economists therefore the incentive involves risk-taking and information problems. The same applies to publishers and promoters but they are better informed because, in general, they have more knowledge about the market value of a work than the author does. Thus, information is asymmetric. Producers use that information to their advantage in a bargaining situation with a creator or performer.

So, copyright may guarantee rights but it does not guarantee how much they earn. It is worth noting that rewards do not have to be financial – economics is not all about money. Moral rights may be more of an incentive to some creators than economic rights and research has shown that many authors value them more highly.

A topic that dominated early discussions of economics of copyright was the extent to which copyright is a *cause* of monopoly. In order to reward authors, prices of creative goods are raised

above the lowest competitive price. That is the trade-off - the incentive to produce works of art etc. against lower access to consumers (readers/music-lovers et al). The question is an old one and applies to other forms of IP, in particular to patents.

Copyright collecting societies, which have monopoly control of the administration of specific rights in copyright, such as the performing right or broadcasting right, have also been a target of competition authorities. Their monopoly has been justified on the grounds of economic efficiency: transaction costs of exercising their rights would be prohibitive for most copyright owners. This is the 'natural monopoly' argument that has long been accepted in economics - it is inefficient to have competing facilities replicating the features (data, policing etc) needed to operate the system of collection and distribution of royalties.

The concept of natural monopoly is now applied to platforms supplying digital works.

Platform economics and network effects

In traditional industries, what limits firm size is the fact that costs and consequently prices eventually rise and demand is accordingly reduced. However, it is also the case that some types of enterprise presented particular problems: the question of how to price the use of networks, such as railways and the National Grid of electricity, recognised that competition in providing them would be inefficient as prices would be higher. They are more efficient as monopolies because costs of production and prices continuously fall as the enterprise expands but on welfare grounds, price regulation is necessary so that they do not exploit that monopoly to the detriment of consumers. This strand of economic theory is now applied in platform economics to the analysis of network pricing.

Platforms are online distributors of goods, mostly produced by other enterprises. They generate network effects along with the collection and exploitation of users' data, one of the most significant novelties of the economics of platforms. There are various types of platforms: resellers, two- and multi-sided. Reseller platforms, such as Amazon, do not produce the goods they sell, acting as solely intermediaries between producer and consumer. Two-sided platforms enable interactions between the sides; card payment systems, such as Visa and e-Bay, enable digital sales to take place. Multi-sided platforms are intermediaries that enable direct interaction between distinct groups of users, facilitating network effects across or within the groups (Bacache-Beauvallet and Bourreau, 2020).

Network effects produce demand-side externalities associated especially with online consumption. They are the source of positive benefits to both sellers and buyers of goods as well

as to users of online services, such as e mail and social media sites. They resemble external benefits which, unlike those in traditional industries, may be internalised, enabling platforms to grow and dominate markets. As the digital creative industries experience massive increasing returns to scale ('scalability') with marginal costs at almost zero, traditional self-regulating forces via the market mechanism fail to inhibit expansion of platforms. The resulting competition issues are significantly different from those in the pre-digital world and are challenging for regulators (Tirole, 2017).

As Aguilar et al (2023) demonstrate, platforms have helped to deliver an unprecedented explosion of new content in books, music, movies, and so forth. They have reduced search costs for new products also benefitting producers. While this has increased consumer welfare by offering greater choice and easy availability, often for free, it has led on the one hand to altering the existing outlets for established professional creators and performers¹ and on the other, to excessive choice for consumers who need guidance through the thicket of newly available works.

Pricing and network effects

A fundamentally new aspect of the pricing of products distributed by platforms is that individual decisions impact on those of others, whether producers or consumers, via network effects. A simple example is email: the value of email to one person depends on how many people she can contact on the network. Prices therefore must be set low (or the service made available for free) in order to incentivise users to join. Online markets are multi-sided with interdependence that requires taking network effects into account. The platform coordinates these effects via its pricing policy. Digital distribution has given rise to new features of price setting and pricing models that are different from those in the 'nuts and bolts' economy (Bacache-Beauvallet, 2020).

A simple case of a two-sided market has been well-known for a long time: a radio station broadcasts for free to listeners, while financing its activities by advertising. How much advertisers are willing to pay depends on the number of listeners, who, however, switch off if there is too much advertising (the 'price' to the listener). The radio station (the platform) has to balance these incentives in its pricing. This two-sided market has zero price on one side (listeners) and a charge on the other (to advertisers) - a case of asymmetric pricing. Listeners

¹ The impact of digitisation on creativity is a little researched topic. I have argued that the effects of digitisation are asymmetric: producers in the creative industries benefit from reduced costs etc but creators and performers do not enjoy the same benefits and so are at an increasing disadvantage in dealing with producers (Towse, 2024).

and advertisers do not interact with each other via the price mechanism in a market but only via prices set by the platform to each side.

A digital age variation on the model is music streaming. Listeners can choose whether to pay a subscription or access music for-free. For-free listeners have access to the bundle of titles the platform has assembled but have to put up with the adverts, while paying consumers (subscribers) pay to avoid them. The platform competes with other streaming services when negotiating the rates it charges to advertisers depending on the number of listeners, who are attracted by the music it offers and its subscription rate, and also according to what it has to pay the record labels.

These are elementary examples but the principles underlie pricing issues in more complex multi-sided markets in which platforms have to juggle network effects not only on each side but also cross-group effects. An example of the latter is dating platforms which charge lower prices to women than men because fewer women (apparently!) use the service; so the more men there are, the lower prices would be to women. Another example of cross group network effects is the low prices charged for game consols to attract more game developers (remember Polaroid – cheap camera, expensive film?).

Multi- vs. single homing cuts across these already complex features. Both buyers and sellers have the option to join competing platforms: radio listeners are likely to multi-home as long as radio stations are free to use and advertisers similarly can advertise on several stations. In music-streaming, listeners are more likely to single-home with one subscription (and most streaming services offer similar or even the same bundle of titles). Switching costs can lead to users sticking to one platform, though, due to the time and trouble of trawling through information about other platforms and loss of platform specific benefits, not just to subscription charges.

Platforms compete for consumers' attention in an era of information overload and incomplete information. Economics of attention demonstrates that even free goods and services present consumers with choices: how much time to spend researching products, platforms and services. Time has an opportunity cost that can be valued monetarily (by wages) and by psychic cost (annoyance etc). In an age of plenty, consumers' attention is a limiting factor. As Herbert Simon perspicaciously observed already in the 1970s: 'a wealth of information creates a poverty of attention'.

Economics of attention

Fifty years on the 'poverty of attention' has become a major problem for consumers and producers. It has spawned a wide-ranging literature in all branches of social science and especially in marketing.²

Consumers 'economise' on the attention devoted to acquiring information, which has opportunity cost in terms of the value of both work and leisure time. Producers of goods and services and platforms compete for consumers' attention through advertising, special offers and various types of non-price competition (see below). Consumers' attention has economic value that is treated by them as an input into the business model. In the two-sided market model, for example in broadcasting, consumers' attention is 'sold' to advertisers, who finance the broadcast programme, which is 'free' to the consumer. Thus the consumer pays a 'price' for the programme through their attention. At the same time, data on consumers is collected and analysed by artificial intelligence, stored and sold on to other platforms.

Non-price competition

Competing platforms with similar offers to buyers may offer add-on services to promote non-price competition, often to one side of the market only. Examples of such services are reviews, recommendations and ratings (Belleflamme and Peitz, 2020). Platforms facilitate the exchange of opinions between consumers on the services they supply (such as reviews of books and music titles) by 'matching' groups of consumers online. Cultural goods differ from 'ordinary' goods in requiring experience and specialist knowledge to inform purchase. You don't buy a book or a painting just according to its price but choose ones with special characteristics to meet your taste. Platforms use the exchange of recommendations and ratings by consumers/users to collect data on consumers' characteristics and then use that to personalise their services. They are not necessarily 'informed' or even reliable, however, as platforms may bias results in their own interest, which is to maximise the number of people using their platform. They could also simply be fakes.

Such non-price strategies are an aspect of online business models as they create network effects that are mainly platform specific and therefore can be utilised in attracting market participants such as advertisers, creating cross-group network effects. Platforms therefore combine non-price and pricing strategies in cross market networks, making for complex

² See https://fr.wikipedia.org/wiki/%C3%89conomie_de_l%27attention (English translation).

entrepreneurial decision-making and difficult challenges to regulators, such as competition authorities.

Have platforms caused a revolutionary change in economics?

Digitisation and the emergence of platforms have radically altered the economic organisation of consumption and delivery of creative goods and services, calling for a new application of industrial economics. The result is the emergence of platform economics. Is this an evolutionary change or a revolution in economic thinking? Several aspects of existing theory are relevant while others have been adapted.

A fundamental change is the need to realign the economics of scarcity with a world of plenty. Since its beginning, the basic tenet of economics was the relative scarcity of resources in relation to needs and wants. The use of resources involves costs and their allocation to one type of production is at the cost of their not being available for another use – the basic and fundamental notion of ‘opportunity cost’ that has always underpinned economics. Economics was (and is) about the allocation of those limited resources to the best uses with the resulting distribution of income, wealth and goods and services. In a capitalist society, that is achieved via the price mechanism, with the debate about the role of the state in intervening in the market mechanism to achieve societal goals. The prices of goods, wage rates and rates of profit on capital are the incentives that determine what gets produced and who benefits from it. The theory of natural monopoly used these basic ideas, adapting them for the case of scalability – ever-increasing returns to scale – making the economic case for regulatory pricing. That model is adopted in platform economics but the theory is difficult to apply to freely distributed goods.

Welfare economics has long recognised that private transactions can have public effects – external costs and benefits – requiring state intervention. Using cars produces pollution costs to others that drivers do not pay for. Taxes and subsidies can be used to compensate for social costs and benefits. Public goods that everyone can benefit from will not be produced by private for-profit producers so public authorities have to step in to provide them (eg immunisation)³. These issues mandate the intervention of the state in the market economy, often through the use of law, ie regulation. However, external effects in the digital economy are different as network effects can be captured by profit-maximising platforms.

³ Not lighthouses, as Coase thought. They were typically erected by charges on ships using the harbour – in other words, are a club good.

Implications for platform regulation

Regulation of platforms and online markets is increasingly called for on various grounds, both economic and non-economic. How should this be done: by changing the law or through economic regulators such as competition authorities? Both are policy instruments open to governments. In the music industry, for example, where streaming has raised questions about fair payment to creators and performers, there have been moves both to change the law and through intervention by competition authorities. Changes to law include contract reversion that gives the creator of a work that unexpectedly became a 'best seller' to take back rights they had transferred or conversely, for a work that was not exploited fully by the publisher, the right to renegotiate the contract. An alternative strategy would be the application of competition law to restrict market power: a recent example is the UK's Competition and Markets Authority's (CMA) investigation of the market for streamed music (CMA 2022). Another topic in this vein is that of 'buy-outs' – one-off payments in a deal to acquire all the rights in a work – which some legislation prevents. These topics have both legal and economic dimensions and it is worth discussing the issues that could determine the choice of policy instrument.

The conclusion of the CMA report is interesting in this context, as it found no basis on competition grounds to intervene in the music streaming market but suggested that the matter of 'under-payment' of performers could be resolved through the law. Leaving aside the point the CMA investigation did not include an analysis of platforms (since at the time its *modus vivendi* was to focus on longstanding entry and exit and harm to consumers, which it felt were not present in the case), it is convenient to use this as a basis for discussing what guidance economics might offer to this choice of instrument.

First off is the point made by the CMA itself – that a full enquiry is expensive and lengthy, so the market could have changed by the time it reached a conclusion. The latter point possibly reflects the typical economist's knee-jerk reaction – that markets sort themselves out – and, indeed, there is some evidence in this case that that had happened even without legally required contract reversion, as contracts to musicians have become more flexible and shorter over the years and with changing conditions.⁴ Minimising transaction costs is a prime economic consideration for regulators and both monopoly investigation and changing the law require costly time and expertise of civil servants and those in the industry.

The economics of regulation also offers some guidance. Public choice theory applies economic methods to political decision-making. While welfare economics conceives of society as the sum

⁴ <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/music-creators-earnings-in-the-digital-era>

of individual members, each of whom make decisions in their own interests, public choice is about decisions that are made collectively through the ballot box or by government officials and administrators. Political parties and government officers are also self-interested and may make decisions based on their interests.

While welfare economics is concerned with market failure, public choice theory deals with government failure. In order to regulate industry, say to control monopoly, civil servants have to understand how an industry functions in detail and for that they have to go to the industry to find out; they can therefore be misinformed or swayed by those in the industry seeking to maintain the monopoly (known as 'regulatory capture'). Industry incumbents would likely have more finance available than a new start-up trying to enter the industry to sway the enquiry in their favour. 'Rent-seeking' is the term in public choice theory for the investment by parties in promoting their interests. To counter that behaviour, government officials would have to incur increased transaction costs in holding an enquiry that offered an impartial view. These ideas throw light on the complexity of regulation and other forms of intervention by government to improve welfare.

Legal versus market solutions

With these considerations in mind, what can be said about how governments seek to improve social welfare: can we say that passing laws is somehow preferable to using economic incentives to solve a problem? Taking the question of contract reversion as an example, is it possible to judge between those two courses of action? Perhaps not, but what can be done is to lay out the pros and cons of each approach.

One question might be what the relative transaction costs are. Clearly the CMA report cited above regarded them as lower for legislation than for a competition enquiry. Whatever they are, though, the question might also arise as to whether the expected increase in copyright holders' earnings would merit the cost of intervention. That is a problem of the distribution of costs and benefits – or to be more precise, of their relative redistribution. The problem is often framed as one of fairness, as if no cost would be too great to achieve it. Unless the parties involved were prepared to underwrite the costs of the intervention, they would fall on tax-payers. It could, of course, be argued that fairness is an important societal value and addressing instances of it wherever they occur benefits us all but there are probably greater instances of lack of fairness that might override the remuneration of performers. It is certainly the case that the cost of maintaining observance of law in general is in everyone's interests, though that may not apply equally strongly to every case.

There is, moreover, the problem mentioned above of what is intended by the concept of fair remuneration in copyright law: it seems to mean more or less 'that which the market will bear'. If that market - say, for music streaming - is competitive, royalty payments would be 'fair', whilst if there is unfair competition on either side (such as a monopoly or tight oligopoly of platforms or of record labels, or dominant trade unions or CMOs), royalty rates would not be fair. If the market were left to itself, would fair deals prevail eventually, as some empirical studies have suggested? It is sometimes argued that the potential threat of intervention provides sufficient incentives to market agents to sort the problem out.

This way of thinking does not solve the legislator's problem of what, if any, action should be taken but it demonstrates the underlying way economists think about it.

Final thoughts

Economics aims to shed light on the organisation of production and consumption both of privately produced goods and services (industrial economics, demand studies) and of public goods and bads (welfare economics, public choice theory) and seeks to test theoretical propositions empirically. The outcome of these endeavours can then be used in drawing up policy. Put the other way round: policy propositions should be based on empirical findings. Research is needed for policy-making on copyright as it is for competition law, or indeed, any other area of government intervention.

A methodological question is how much of the analysis of platforms is ad hoc and basically just generalisation from practice. Platform economics explains platforms as huge natural monopolies that only internal incentives such as management limitations can halt; there are no 'physical barriers', such as limitations of plant size, as in previous industrial economics, implying ever greater expansion of their size and scope. In theoretical terms, welfare economics treats *external* effects as requiring state intervention to correct market over- or under-production (due to social costs or benefits); public choice theory relates to the problems of regulatory intervention. What were external effects in the pre-digital era, however, are now internalised by private enterprise in the world of digital production and lead to ever-increasing size of producers and platforms, requiring ever stronger regulatory intervention. Consumers' attention and ability to absorb information and devote time to the acquisition of goods is one of the few limiting factors in this story.

These theories continue to be used in the regulation of industry. What platform economics demonstrates, though, is that the task for regulators is massively more complex in the digital economy.

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